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Effect of soil type and rainfall on *Acacia senegal* (L.) Willd. Gum viscosity

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Abstract—The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of site factors namely; soil types and rainfall on viscosity of gum Arabic from (*Acacia senegal*). Samples of gum arabic were collected from sites representing three main soil types viz (sand, clay and sandy clay or “gardud” under three rainfall (low, medium and high) conditions throughout the gum belt of North, South Kordofan and Blue Nile States. Gum viscosity was measured using a Brookfield Viscometer (MYR Viscometer – version L spindle 3 speed 200 RPM) and pH-meter. Analysis of variance was used to determine the differences in viscosity and pH of gums from different sites affected by soils type and rainfall. Correlation and regression analysis revealed high average viscosity for gums produced under low rainfall conditions in sand and clay soils, as well as also in gardud soil under medium rainfall. Sand in medium rainfall, gardud in high rainfall and clay in medium and high rainfall produced low average viscosity gum with significant differences between them and the above mentioned main factors. The results also showed that there were no significant differences in pH for all gum samples obtained from different soil types and different rainfall levels. Regression analysis showed a linear relationship ($R^2 = 0.87-0.99$) between viscosity and concentration of gum Arabic from the different sites. According to the results of this study gum Arabic could be classified according to viscosity into high (80-85 cps) medium (69-70 cps) and low (<60 cps) viscosity.

Keywords—*Acacia senegal*, Gum Arabic, Rainfall, Soil type, Viscosity

INTRODUCTION

Natural gums are polysaccharides obtained as exudates from different parts of different plants. They are produced by different countries in different environments, mostly tropical or sub-tropical. Commercially the most widely used natural gums are gum Arabic, guar gum, gum tragacanth, gum karaya, locust bean gum and gum ghatti. Gum Arabic (Hashab) is the second most widely used natural gum which is produced by the *Acacia senegal* (L.) Willd tree.

Viscosity is a very important polymer property that describes its solution’s fluidity and it relates to the thickness and adhesiveness of the solution. Viscosity is a resistance of shearing or flow of liquid systems. Viscosity can range from high (thick gel) to low viscosity.

Viscosity of gum Arabic solution is affected by a number of factors which include the age of the parent tree, rainfall during the harvesting season, time of exudation and type of storage conditions. Thus viscosities of solutions of gum Arabic of similar grades can vary by as much as more than 50% and are affected differently by concentration, temperature, pH, salt content and presence of other electrolytes [4]. Gum Arabic as found in nature exists as a natural or slightly acidic calcium, magnesium, potassium or sodium salt of complex polysaccharides [4] [5] and [6] reported that the different metal ions present in gum Arabic molecules affect the gum Arabic viscosity, where monovalent ions increase gum viscosity while divalent ions decrease it. However, research directed towards relating soil type containing these metal ions and rainfall to the viscosity of gum Arabic is lacking.

Therefore, the main objective was to investigate some of the main factors that affect gum viscosity such as variation in soil and climate factors. The specific objectives were:

To determine the effects of rainfall and soil type on gum viscosity.

To explore the range of viscosity variation in gum Arabic in the important gum producing areas in the gum belt.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Gum samples were obtained from three different provenances in different ecological zones of the gum arabic belt within three rainfall isohyets (high, low and moderate). The experiment was carried out in three types of soils of the *A. senegal* belt (Clay, “gardud” or sandy clay and sandy soil). Zone one lies in the clay soil with low rainfall (350-450 mm) was represented by Karkog area. Zone two and three were represented by Eldaly and Bout, in moderate (500-600 mm) and high (700-900 mm) rainfall isohyets, respectively. Elodaya, Elfula and Elmoglad in west Kordofan represent the low (250- 350 mm), moderate (400-500 mm) and high (500-600 mm) rainfall isohyets in gardud soils, respectively. The sandy soil area was represented by Bara, El Himaira and Babanosa for low (150-200 mm), moderate (250-350 mm) and high (450-500 mm) rainfall isohyets, respectively.

Hashab trees in the different areas were randomly selected, marked and tapped for gum samples. The gum samples (81 samples) obtained from tapping the trees were dried to 105°C to be ready for preparation of gum solutions. Gum solutions of 10 % concentration were prepared and kept in a refrigerator. Benzoic acid was used for solution conservation. Also gum

solution of different concentrations viz 5%, 10%... 35% were prepared.

Viscosity and pH of the different gum solutions were measured using Brookfield viscometer (MYR viscometer-version L spindle 3, speed 200 rpm) and pH-meter.

The data were analyzed using the statistical software's namely; (SAS), JMP and EXCEL statistical packages. Analysis of variance and Duncan's New Multiple Range Test at $P \leq 0.05$ probability level was used to separate the mean. Linear regression analysis was also used to study the relationship of gum viscosity and gum solution concentration. Correlation analysis between viscosity and the different studied factors was performed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study showed that the viscosity of gum Arabic obtained from different areas in the gum belt, ranges from 50-130 cps averaging 67.7 cps for gum solution of 10 % concentration Table (1). This result is in agreement with [1] who stated that the viscosity of gum Arabic varied according to the type and variety of the gum itself. The same author also noted that viscosity given by good quality gum Arabic at 10 % concentration at 25° C was approximately 100 cps.

Table 2 shows the effect of different soil types within the different rainfall isohyets on pH and viscosity of gum Arabic. The results revealed that viscosity increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in sandy soils compared to gardud and clay soils under high rainfall. The gardud and clay soils were not significantly different from each other. Under moderate rainfall, the viscosity of gum produced in gardud soil was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than that produced in sandy and clay soils. Viscosity of gum produced on sand and clay soils were not significantly different from each other. Under low rainfall all the soils produced high viscosity of gum with no significant differences between them. Generally, the highest gum viscosity was given by the sandy and clay soils with the exception of viscosity in gardud under moderate rainfall.

Gum Arabic produced by the different soils of the gum belt under the different rainfall levels has an acidic reaction ($pH < 7$) and there were no significant differences between pH in the different soil types under the different rainfall conditions. [7] Stated that viscosity decreases in the presence of electrolytes due to charge screening and low pH when the carboxy 1 group become undissociated.

These results clearly demonstrate a relationship between rainfall and soil. Low rainfall produced higher gum viscosity in all three soil types, while high rainfall gave an increase in viscosity in sandy soils with significant difference compare to other soil types. The moderate rainfall has a positive effect on the viscosity of gums produced in gardud soil. These values are significantly different, indicating the effect of the different site factors and hence reflect the influence of the site factors on physicochemical properties of gum produced. The pH values (4.5-4.8) of gum Arabic obtained from different sites in this study were within the range of international specifications (pH: 4.2-4.8) [2].

Figures 1-3 show the relationship between viscosity and concentration of gum Arabic solution for all sample sites.

These figures reflect a linear relationship between viscosity and concentration of gum Arabic solution for concentrations of 5% up to 30% with very good fit of R^2 ranging from 0.87-0.99 for the different figures. This result is in agreement with [5] and [3] who claimed that gum Arabic solutions exhibit Newtonian behavior that could be expressed by a linear relationship between viscosity and concentration of up to 35%. This is explained by the fact that the latter are linear molecules and intermolecular entanglements can readily occur while this is not the case for the highly compact, branched gum Arabi molecules.

Table 1: VISCOSITY AND pH OF GUM ARABIC COLLECTED FROM THREE DIFFERENT RAINFALL ISOHYETS AND THREE TYPES OF SOIL

Site/Rainfall	Clay			Gardud		Sand	
	Sample	Viscosity	pH	Viscosity	pH	Viscosity	pH
High	S11	60	4.83	70	5.01	60	5.13
	S12	50	4.78	40	4.96	90	4.95
	S13	50	4.44	50	4.55	70	4.8
	S21	50	4.54	70	4.49	80	4.77
	S22	50	4.47	60	4.54	60	4.71
	S23	70	4.46	50	4.56	60	4.68
	S31	50	4.5	50	4.55	60	4.61
	S32	60	4.5	60	4.58	60	4.63
	S33	60	4.49	60	4.55	80	4.61
Mean		55.56	4.56	55.67	4.64	68.89	4.76
Medium	S11	70	5.21	70	4.94	70	5.02
	S12	50	4.68	70	4.87	50	4.63
	S13	60	4.59	60	4.66	50	4.64
	S21	50	4.52	60	4.54	50	4.73
	S22	50	4.54	90	4.55	70	5.01
	S23	60	4.42	110	4.55	50	4.64
	S31	50	4.52	60	4.54	50	4.72
	S32	50	4.46	110	4.63	50	4.63
	S33	60	4.44	100	4.66	60	4.73
Mean		55.55	4.59	81.11	4.66	55.55	4.75
Low	S11	100	5.42	120	5.11	90	5.13
	S12	130	4.42	70	4.72	90	5.06
	S13	90	4.4	70	4.62	70	4.93
	S21	70	4.37	40	4.57	70	4.73
	S22	80	4.39	50	4.58	110	4.74
	S23	70	4.4	90	4.53	100	4.68
	S31	60	4.41	50	4.49	80	4.72
	S32	60	4.45	60	4.5	70	4.76
	S33	60	4.52	80	4.48	90	4.72
Mean		80	4.53	70	4.62	85.55	4.83

The gum Arabic viscosity produced in the different soils and different rainfall levels are shown in figure (4). The results showed that there are three classes of viscosity that can be identified: the first class with high viscosity (80-85 cps)

produced in sandy soil under low rainfall, in gardud soil under medium rainfall and in clay soil under low rainfall. The second class is a medium viscosity (69-70 cps) found in sandy soil under high rainfall and in gardud soil under low rainfall. The third class is low viscosity (<60 cps) in gardud soil under high rainfall, sandy soil under medium rainfall and in clay soil under medium high rainfall.

TABLE II: EFFECT OF RAINFALL AND SOIL TYPE ON VISCOSITY AND PH OF GUM ARABIC

RAINFALL (MM)		SOIL TYPE	VISCOSITY/CPS	PH
High	(400-450)	Sand	68.8 a	4.76 a
	(500-600)	Gardud	56.6 b	4.64 a
	(700-900)	Clay	56.6 b	4.56 a
Moderate	(400-500)	Gardud	81.11 a	4.66 a
	(250-350)	Sand	55.56 b	4.75 a
	(500-600)	Clay	55.56 b	4.59 a
Low	(150-200)	Sand	85.56 a	4.83 a
	(350-450)	Clay	80.00 a	4.53 a
	(250-350)	Gardud	70.00 a	4.62 a

Fig 1. The relationship between viscosity and concentration of gum Arabic solution of gum collected from three different rainfall areas in clay soil.

Note:

- 1/ High rainfall (Bout)
Viscosity/cps = -2 + 5.257 concentration% (R Square = 0.89)
- 2/ Medium rainfall (Bozy)

Viscosity/cps = 17.333 + 4.057 concentration% (R Square = 0.87)

3/ Low rainfall (Ocalma)

Viscosity/cps = 10.67 + 4.34 concentration% (R Square = 0.90)

Fig 2. The relationship between viscosity and concentration of gum arabic solution of gum collected from three different rainfall areas in gardud soil.

Note:

- 1/ High rainfall (Elmojled)
Viscosity/cps = 18 + 3.257 concentration% (R Square = 0.98)
- 2/ Medium rainfall (Elfola)
Viscosity/cps = 10 + 4 concentration% (R Square = 0.95)
- 3/ Low rainfall (Elodaya)
Viscosity/cps = 18 + 3.542 concentration% (R Square = 0.98)

Figure 3. The relationship between viscosity and concentration of gum Arabic solution of gum collected from three different rainfall areas in sandy soil.

Note:

- 1/ High rainfall (Babnosa)

Viscosity/cps = 24 + 3.485 concentration% (R Square = 0.92)

2/ Medium rainfall (El Himaira)

Viscosity/cps = 15.333 + 3.028 concentration% (R Square = 0.98)

3/ Low rainfall (Bara)

Viscosity/cps = 12.667 + 4.228 concentration% (R Square = 0.99)

Figure 4. Classification of viscosity of gum arabic as related to soil type and rainfall.

V. CONCLUSION

- Rainfall isohyets of 150-500 mm may give the best quality gum arabic in terms of viscosity magnitude depending upon the soil type.
- Low rainfall in different soils and medium rainfall in gardud soils represented the suitable condition for the best gum quality.
- High rainfall in gardud and clay soil and medium rainfall in sand and clay gave the lowest gum quality in the gum belt.
- There were direct relationships between viscosity in gardud soils in medium rainfall areas and pH value, which could be one of the reasons of increased viscosity in this area in addition to other factors which were not discussed in this study.
- Gum arabic can be classified according to its viscosity.

IV REFERNCES

- [1]. Ballal, M, E, 2002, Yield trends of gum arabic from Acacia senegal as related to some environmental and managerial factors, Ph.D Thesis, University of Khartoum, 105pp.
- [2]. FAO (1996). A review of production, markets and quality control of gum arabic in Africa. FAO, Rome.
- [3]. Glicksman, M and Mitchell, J. R. 1979. Polysaccharides in Food. In Blanchard T.M.V. (eds.) Butterwoths, London.
- [4]. Glicksman, M and sand, R. E. 1973. Industrial Gum, 2nd ed, Wistle,r Academic Press. 197-263.
- [5]. Mahmoud, A. E. 1983. Viscosity modification of gum arabic as a means of enhancing marketability, M.Sc. Thesis, Faculty of Forest Products, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, Virginia, USA.
- [6]. Obied, N.M. 2003. The effect of various cations on gum arabic viscosity, M.Sc. Thesis, Faculty of Forestry, Khartoum University.
- [7]. Williams, P, A and Phillips, G, O (1998). Gums and stabilizer for food industry 9 Royal Society of Chemistry. Cambridge UK. Publication No 218.